

<https://doi.org/10.28925/1609-8595.2022.4.2>

UDC 37.091:[343.226:364.633]

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SEXUAL HARASSMENT AND SEXTORTION IN UNIVERSITIES AS AN ACTUAL SCIENTIFIC PROBLEM

This article explores the issues of harassment in the university environment. The concept of sextortion in education would be taken as a basis. This problem is now being actively studied by scientists from all over the world, which indicates its importance and attempts to scientifically substantiate ways to prevent and fight this phenomenon. The study also focuses on aspects of the cultural manifestation of this illegal phenomenon in education, namely cinema and the media. The most important factor that declares the importance of a particular phenomenon in society is its reflection in popular culture and its discourse. The problem of sextortion in education is undoubtedly such. It should be clarified that this applies mainly to the countries of the Western world, but in Ukraine this problem is also very relevant in the educational environment of universities. The article provides specific examples of inappropriate sexual behavior in educational institutions and analyzes the problem from various sides and subjects of involvement. In addition, the very concept of sextortion and its genesis are analyzed. The study cites the factors that most often lead to the manifestation of sextortion in education. In addition to all of the above, the consequences of this phenomenon on the part of the victim are analyzed, where the key consequence of sexual claims is the impact on the emotional state of a person: victim becomes more vulnerable and feels insecure, being in eternal fear. Is it normal when a future specialist, mastering his profession, cannot feel calm? The authors also offer recommendations for countering and preventing this phenomenon in the university environment with an emphasis on preventive measures, but with the observance of procedures to avoid slander and denunciations of objectionable participants in the educational process.

Keywords: *harassment; institutions of higher education; mass culture; prevention; sextortion.*

Introduction. Every year, the topic of sexual violence in culture, politics, journalism, law enforcement, and medicine dominates the headlines of foreign articles, such as the BBC and Vanity Fair (Walsh, 2022), as well as leading mass media of Ukraine, such as the TV channel TNS (Sulyma, 2021). Let's emphasize that these days Metoo has called sexual harassment a global epidemic that has covered all spheres of life (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020). The attention of the press was especially focused on the stories of harassment

of Ukrainian actors Volodymyr Talashko (Bida, 2021), Volodymyr Vladimirov (Minyaylo, 2020), Hollywood actors Chris Noth (White, 2021) and Kevin Spacey, screenwriter and Oscar winner Paul Haggis (Jones, 2018), film producer Harvey Weinstein (BBC News, 2022), former Chelsea coach Abraham Grant (Hughes, 2022). And this is only a small part of the list of media figures who were noticed in sexual harassment.

It was established that the problem of violence also affected institutions of higher education. According

to the conclusions of MeToo, sexual harassment has become an «epidemic in the system of higher education» (Smyk, 2021), which certainly affected the mental state of students, their perception of the future profession. In particular, according to the results of research by the Institute of Mass Information in cooperation with the public association «Women in the Media» (IMI, 2021) and surveys by «YurFem» (YurFem, 2019), harassment «deeply affects individuals, groups or even organizations». Specialists who have dealt with the indicated issues (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020) have identified key signs that contribute to sexual harassment: instability in study and work conditions, a culture of silence, a toxic environment, and a lack of active leadership.

As part of the project «Updating issues of sexual harassment at universities» an anonymous survey was conducted among students of various higher education institutions and it was found that about 45% of the respondents had heard expressions from teachers and university employees or noticed actions on their part with sexual connotations; 37.5% are aware of cases of sexual harassment at their universities; and only half of the respondents know where to apply if they have become a victim of sexual harassment (YurFem, 2019).

Problem statement. It is worth noting that not all victims talk about what happened to them: most are ashamed to turn to law enforcement agencies, state authorities or, at least, to the management of universities or faculties. Gossip «creeps» among the student community, but it does not provide the publicity necessary for action. Silence, which occurs in most cases, provokes a feeling of fear of the teaching staff on the part of students.

The goal is to highlight the degree of study of the problem of sexual harassment and inclination to intimate relationships in the environment of higher education institutions in domestic and foreign scientific literature and specific examples from mass culture, to provide recommendations on ways to prevent and overcome cases of sexual violence in higher education institutions of Ukraine, including through existing programs of domestic, European and American psychologists and sociologists.

Methodology. Among the research methods used, the following were decisive: analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological sources, government documents on the topic of research for the theoretical justification of the highlighted problem, modeling, synthesis of the obtained data. A content analysis of the manifestations of harassment in popular culture, namely in cinema and content production, was carried out. Through open sources (news, reports of human rights organizations, etc.), cases of harassment in the universities of Ukraine and the world were investigated.

Research results. The analysis of scientific sources, fiction and cinematography allows us to state that the

problem of sexual violence and sexual harassment in institutions of higher education, unlike most other European countries, the USA or Canada, is almost never raised in Ukraine (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020; Bloom, Sorin, Wagman & Oaks, 2021; Edwards, Rodenhizer & Eckstein, 2020). After all, against the background of foreign tapes, we did not find a single domestic one that would reveal the stated problem of the research. In our opinion, this state of affairs is connected with the strategy of silencing similar cases in Ukrainian society. We ourselves impose a kind of taboo on this subject, for our own reasons: it is simply unpleasant to hear and dig into it, «reputation is more important», «the student may be to blame, who knows», «there are much more important problems».

Unlike Ukraine, in leading foreign countries mass media, publicists, and writers cover the issue of violence on various platforms and in various forms (Walsh, 2022; Hughes, 2022; White, 2021). Thus, the problem of sexual harassment becomes a subject of public discussion in fiction, and more strongly in cinematography, that is, it occupies a place in the cultural discourse of society.

Let's emphasize that in foreign TV series this topic is primarily highlighted when revealing the problems faced by both schoolchildren and students of educational institutions. For example, the series «Ray Donovan», «13 Reasons Why», «Black Lagoon» and Riverdale, as well as the films «Garbiel's Inferno» and «Favorite Teacher». In various films, directors present the problem of sexual violence in educational institutions. The named series mainly deal with the problem of harassment in high schools and colleges and cover both violence between students themselves and sexual harassment by teachers.

For example, in «Ray Donovan», only a few episodes are devoted to the problem of harassment, which tell about the problems of the main character's daughter in college and her «relationship» with the teacher of higher mathematics. And «13 Reasons Why» describes all possible problems of teenagers, touches on every «black» side of high school. The authors try to draw the attention of adults to adolescent problems, to the possible violence that children may face, both from peers and from teachers. It is difficult to single out one or two feature films in which the school coach or the coach of a student team, such as a football team, would not act as a rapist. Examples can be episodes of the TV series «Legends of Tomorrow» and «Thinking Like a Criminal», the main characters of which were victims of abuse by their sports manager in childhood.

It has been established that sexual harassment has long been an unaddressed problem (McKinnon, 1979). In the study of sexual harassment in higher education institutions, quite a variety of issues are brought to the fore: unwanted pregnancy, direct or tangential consequences of poverty (the need for financial support). Quite specific problems are also regularly solved, for

example, the demand of male teachers for sexual services from female students so that the latter can get higher current grades or even a diploma upon completion of studies (Moskaliuk, 2022).

It is the latter that can be singled out as the definition of sextortion – a type of corrupt activity, which consists in the abuse of power to obtain «sexual gain» or certain advantages associated with it. This concept is relatively new. It was first formulated by the International Association of Women Judges (IAWJ) in 2008. Studies show that women are more likely to demand sexual services, but this problem also affects men, transpeople and people whose gender identity or gender expression does not meet the social and cultural expectations of a particular society (International Association of Women Judges, 2022). Sextortion is criminalized in many countries of the world, but it should be emphasized that only formally.

It was established that the problem raised by us became the subject of active discussion not only by representatives of the mass media and cinematography, but also by scientists of many foreign countries (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020; Bloom, Sorin, Wagman & Oaks, 2021; Edwards, Rodenhizer & Eckstein, 2020). The analysis of a number of articles on the specified issue testifies, firstly, to the efforts of researchers to give a clear definition of the essence of the concept of «sextortion», its main characteristics and signs. Thus, the author of the publication «SEX + CORRUPTION = SEXORTION», Amalia Sauket, raising the issue of sexual corruption and harassment (Syauket, A. & Wijanarko, 2022), emphasizes that it is important to distinguish sextortion from other sexual and corruption crimes. According to her definition, some offenses may include coercion into intimate relations, but not have a corruption component, or vice versa. Then they cannot be qualified as sextortion.

As for the very concept of «sextortion», it arose in 2008 – it was proposed by the IAWJ. The closest translation of this word is «sexual extortion». According to the IAWJ's definition, sexual extortion consists of two components: corrupt behavior by a party in power and forced sexual activity. «Sextortion» includes the concepts of «sexual exploitation», «forced sexual activity», «abuse» and «harassment».

According to the IAWJ study (International Association of Women Judges, 2022), sextortion must be distinguished as a corrupt act from other forms of sexual coercion, such as sexual harassment or sexual solicitation, online coercion. According to the contributor's conclusions, two components are necessary for the specified action to be classified as sextortion:

1. Sexual: involves an implicit or explicit request to engage in any form of unwanted sexual activity, which can range from sexual intercourse to unwanted touching of exposed body parts and phrases.

2. Corruption: persons who demand sexual favors

must occupy positions of authority, which they abuse, seeking to exact sexual intercourse in exchange for their performance of certain «work» moments.

In order to determine in which cases it is corruption and when actions can be considered sextortion, according to the conclusions of the author of the publication «Sextortion in Education Sector and Response to Criminal Legal System in Tanzania», Kambug Yusuf, the following three conditions must be present (Yusuph, 2016):

1. Abuse of power.
2. Quid pro quo or «this for that».
3. Psychological coercion, physical pressure.

We emphasize that according to the conclusions given in the above-mentioned work of Kambug Yusuf, cases of sexual harassment and other forms of sexual nature, such as ill-treatment or gender-based violence, provided that the above three conditions are not present, are not considered acts of corruption. As an example, the author cites a case of sexual harassment in the workplace, in which there is no quid pro quo condition, which can be defined not as corruption, but rather as one of the other types of violence.

The author of the study on the problem of CyberSextortion, O'Malley and Holt (2022), also raise the problem of establishing the nature of actions that have signs of sextortion. According to them, cases of sexting occur in two ways: in-person relationships/actions (about 60% of cases) and online relationships/actions (about 40% of cases). The second type does not exclude personal acquaintance with the criminal, but claims of illegal acts through the Internet.

Developing this opinion, we can say that there is another variation of the definition of sextortion. This definition is related to Internet communication and activities in the digital environment. «Sextortion», as noted by O'Malley and Holt, is the practice of extorting money, sex, or other favors by threatening victims to share their intimate photos, audio, text, video, or other media online or through closed social groups (O'Malley & Holt, 2022). According to the authors' conclusion, such actions can be interpreted as cyberbullying.

The age and demographic features of the victims are also the subject of careful study by researchers dealing with issues of sextortion. It should be noted that the authors of a number of works, including Hazel Feigenblatt (2020), «Breaking the silence around sextortion» and Justin V. Patchin and Samir Hinduja (2020), «Sextortion Among Adolescents: Results from a National Survey of U.S. Youth», claim that the majority of victims (>60%) are persons under the age of eighteen: of them, representatives of the female and male genders are roughly equal.

It was found that the authors of the studies, in which various aspects of the phenomenon under investigation are violated, pay great attention to the issues of countering and preventing sextortion. According to their

conclusion, this is the field, first of all, of criminology. As for prevention, based on the analysis of Amalia Sauket's work (2022), «SEX + CORRUPTION = SEXORTION», such actions can be conditionally divided into three levels or steps, namely primary, secondary and tertiary. Primary prevention, according to the researcher, should be aimed at community prevention, starting from the family environment. Secondary prevention identifies and predicts the potential for crime by looking at social reality. Regarding tertiary prevention, according to the author of the article, «it is an attempt to make a certain agreement with the criminal act so that it does not happen again; that is, upon the fact of committing the first» (Syauket & Wijanarko, 2022).

Preventive measures for the victims themselves, as the researcher notes (Thomas, 2015; Moneva, Miró-Llinares & Hart, 2021), consist in ignoring the demands of the criminal. Victims of sexting must find a way to report the fact of the crime, otherwise there will be more and more victims. As for the apparatus, through the moralizing system, namely prevention: it is necessary to strengthen moral values, to suppress the animal instincts of people, through, for example, trainings.

The conducted research shows that in the foreign scientific space, articles devoted to the issue of sexual harassment in the educational environment have their proper place. Thus, in the educational context, as noted by the authors of the publication «Threat of sexual assault among female students in Tanzania», Peter, S., & Malyi, M. (2013), sexual harassment is extremely reprehensible sexual behavior that violates equal rights to receive education. Students, mostly girls, at different levels of education (primary, high school, colleges and universities) often face various types of sexual harassment, one of which is sexual harassment. Such harassment caused serious physical and psychological damage (Athuman, 2012).

For example, Yusuph K. (2016) describes the problem of sextortion in educational institutions in Tanzania, where it is gaining new momentum every time. In 2013, Tanzania's Deputy Minister of Social Protection, Gender and Children, Ummi, Mwalim, addressing the House of Parliament, stated that sextortion is increasing in higher education institutions. She noted that college and university professors force female students to provide sexual favors in exchange for improving their grades. The report documented a case of suicide of a female student in connection with similar illegal actions of a teacher.

In Ukraine, there are no such «informal» mentions of sexual violence in universities and countermeasures against it, but every year more and more documents on the prevention of sexual violence in higher education institutions appear, and various methods of counteraction and punishment are being developed.

With the renewal of concepts and points of view in this matter, sociologists focused on new forms of interaction (Barak, 2005): sexual harassment on the

Internet. It would seem that the nightly correspondence between a teacher and a first-year student, for example, does not carry any threat: the discussion of musical compositions, films, works of art. But at a certain moment, «control» over the situation can be lost, and the messages will have a completely different character, so to speak, «seductive», the teacher offers to conduct a personal tour of the classrooms or research laboratories, invites home tutoring. This type of sexual violence is called sexting (Barak, 2005).

Note that student complaints about the problems of sexual harassment in universities are not unfounded. This is confirmed by a study of Charles University in Prague, conducted in eleven universities in the Czech Republic. 80 percent of the students surveyed complained that they were victims of sexual harassment or witnessed such situations. The results of the studies presented in (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020) show that only every fourth female student reports claims from teachers. But if you add other forms of violence, the numbers double.

Sexual harassment of teachers can be directed not only at the female part of the audience. Male students are also sometimes coerced into sexual relations with student teachers. A similar thing happened in one of the universities of the city of Pisa, namely the «groping» of students.

In addition, it is worth noting that the teacher cannot always be the initiator of this type of «cooperation»: when a student tries to seduce the teacher in order to get some privileges, including good grades, in a separate course. A student's pregnancy in such relationships can provoke blackmail on her part, especially if her «partner» is married. But this does not mean that the blame is removed from the teacher. After all, the teacher must also understand what he agrees to, what responsibility it entails, understand that although he did not demand anything by force, he still receives a certain benefit. In addition, it is worth remembering that the teacher can record your offer, and offering a bribe is a crime and entails legal or criminal liability.

In many universities, the statutes prohibit relations between teachers and students, for example, in the V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University (The regulation on the settlement of conflict situations at V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, 2020), but the very fact of the existence of such relations does not indicate the existence of corruption as such. After all, we are only talking about coercion into sexual relations, about obtaining benefits for both parties: evaluation and «satisfaction» of needs.

If we speak specifically, we can cite a number of situations that have been highlighted in the Ukrainian press over the past 5–6 years. One of the last, in February 2022, was an incident at the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv: the rector was charged with molesting female students (link). In

addition, the article discussed the correspondence of the Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv library director with a 16-year-old female student on intimate topics (VGORODE, 2022). In the winter of 2019, female students accused associate professor Petr Romanenko, a botany teacher, of unethical behavior: that he harassed them during practice in the Kaniv reserve (RBC (2019).

If we analyze the situation at other universities, then in 2021 a statement was made in the press that Volodymyr Talashko, a teacher at the Karpenko-Kary University, was the culprit of the sex scandal at the above-mentioned university. After the publicity, the actor wrote an application for dismissal of his own free will and rejected all the accusations against him. The management of the university reported that all the data collected in this case were handed over to law enforcement agencies (Sulyma, 2021). In 2017, another teacher of the «cultural» direction, the head of the choreography department of the Rivne State Humanitarian University, Volodymyr Godovsky, was publicly accused of harassment. After the statement of one of the students, immediately 13 students and graduates of the department, and even colleagues, agreed to talk about their «acquaintance» with the teacher: «I was still lucky, because I heard about cases when he bent the stick. That is, he did not just touch female students, but openly offered sex. I think it's just immoral. For him, this is a payment option. If a girl has no money, she can pay with her own body» (Hromadske, 2017).

In order to counteract and prevent manifestations of sextortion in the field of education, it is necessary to build a principled hierarchy, to set appropriate ethical frameworks. And after that, include all participants of the educational process in this «context». A real example of such counteraction can be represented by the document concluded by the management of the Rivne State Humanitarian University on the prevention and fight against sexual harassment at the university (Regulations on the policy of preventing and combating sexual harassment at the Rivne State Humanitarian University, 2019). It contains a course of action for students who have experienced sexual harassment by a teacher, a form for filing a complaint and a description of the procedure for handling the latter. A similar document was issued on the basis of Vinnytsia Agrarian University.

The more the topic of sexual violence is publicized in informal sources, the less fear students will have about this topic. Literature, podcasts, and cinema influence the worldview and perception of situations by today's youth. As a rule, the subtext of the works is to prevent the spread of violence in education. For example, the creators of the above-mentioned TV series «13 Reasons Why» created a support site for victims of bullying, sexual violence, and psychological problems (Suicide Prevention Resource Center, 2022).

In addition to all of the above, the key consequence of sexual harassment, in our opinion, is the impact on

a person's emotional state: he becomes more vulnerable and feels unprotected, being in constant fear. And is it normal when a future specialist, mastering his profession, cannot feel at ease (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020)? Fear paralyzes. It brings a person back to that terrible moment, causes dislike and a distorted perception of everything that «surrounded» that event.

A complete ban on communication between teachers and students outside of school is incorrect and impossible to control. After all, there are also exceptions: communication can be interesting and soulful and really take place within the limits of ethical norms. Sexual harassment is a manifestation of the inability of the current higher education system to address its own shortcomings. Universities around the world are struggling to protect their students from the horrific life experiences of being harassed or solicited for sexual favors. Such an example of anti-sextortion mechanisms at work is at the University of California, Berkeley. They provide a confidential communication channel for victims, create safe zones, require all students and staff to report inappropriate behavior among colleagues and, most importantly, adopt an internal policy that prohibits such behavior. Violations of this policy will initiate sanctions and the matter will be referred to law enforcement. There is no terminological apparatus for defining «sextortion» in the US, and neither do we. But here it is also a matter of the difference in the mentality of the country's citizens. The biggest blow is not that this phenomenon takes place in the field of education, but that people who know about it remain silent and do not oppose it (Alrabe et al., 2017).

Sometimes a person can exaggerate the level of attention paid to him by one or another person. Every touch, hug, phrase said with a smile on the face is perceived as a courtship, oppression of rights. So it is worth being able to distinguish between the prerequisites for harassment by the same teacher and just a good attitude. In connection with the latter, various groups of sociologists have developed a number of tests and questionnaires that allow you to determine whether the teacher really wants something more from you than just good communication (YurFem, 2019).

It is worth focusing on the legal aspect, namely on two articles of the Criminal Code of Ukraine: Art. 153 «Sexual violence» and Art. 154 «Compulsion to engage in sexual intercourse». The first of them is much broader, and can be «applied» not only in the case of direct intimacy. The punishment in both cases is imprisonment for up to 5 years and up to 6 months, respectively.

No one says that during your education you will necessarily have to become a participant in the situations stated in the study, a victim of sexual violence, but you must be prepared for the emergence of such problems and the need for meaningful actions in the situation. The main thing is to remember self-respect, that any grades are not worth such humiliation, that you are not

alone with your problem and there are always those who will help you.

Conclusions. Sexual harassment is now a named and articulated problem. There are a number of concepts, strategies and preventive practices to combat this problem in the educational environment, especially in higher education, it is worth noting that new approaches and practices are constantly being developed.

The problem of sexual violence and sextortion in institutions of higher education requires the development of new and innovative preventive methods and the organization of support structures; preparation of the legal framework; needs expanding the audience, encouraging to talk about it, using, first of all, the most popular resources: books and films, that is, general social activation and attention to this problem.

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СЕКСУАЛЬНІ ДОМАГАННЯ ТА СЕКСТОРШЕН У ЗАКЛАДАХ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ ЯК НАУКОВА ПРОБЛЕМА

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Ця стаття досліджує питання харасменту в університетському середовищі. За основу взято концепт сексторшен в освіті. Ця проблема зараз активно вивчається вченими з усього світу, що свідчить про її значущість та спроби науково обґрунтувати шляхи профілактики та боротьби з цим явищем. Дослідження також зосереджує свою увагу на аспектах культурного прояву цього протиправного явища в освіті, а саме в кінематографі та засобах масової інформації. Найважливішим фактором, який заявляє про важливість того чи іншого явища в суспільстві, є його відображення в масовій культурі та її дискурсі. Проблема сексторшен в освіті безперечно такою є. Необхідно уточнити, що це стосується переважно країн Західного світу, але й в Україні ця проблема також є дуже актуальною в освітньому середовищі університетів. У статті наводяться конкретні приклади неналежної сексуальної поведінки в закладах освіти та проводиться аналіз проблеми з різних сторін та суб'єктів залучення. Крім цього, аналізується саме поняття сексторшен та його генезис. У дослідженні наводяться чинники, які найчастіше призводять до прояву сексторшен в освіті. У статті аналізуються наслідки цього явища з боку жертви, де ключовим наслідком сексуальних домагань є вплив на емоційний стан людини: вона стає більш вразливою і почувається незахищеною, перебуваючи у вічному страху. Також авторами пропонується рекомендації для протидії та профілактики цього явища в університетському середовищі з акцентом на превентивні заходи, але з дотриманням процедур, щоб уникнути наклепів та доносів на неугодних учасників освітнього процесу.

Ключові слова: *домагання; заклади вищої освіти; масова культура; профілактика; сексторшен.*

Received 15.11.2022

Accepted 20.12.2022